

EXPLORING AI IN EDUCATION THROUGH INTERDISCIPLINARY COLLABORATION

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Abstract

In an era where technology has the potential to rapidly transform every aspect of our lives, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education stands at a crossroads. On the one hand, AI offers unprecedented opportunities to personalize learning, enhance pedagogical approaches, and bridge educational gaps. On the other, it raises critical concerns about data privacy, algorithmic bias, and equitable access. This paper explores how an interdisciplinary hub dedicated to AI in education (AIED) aims to help navigate these dualities.

AI in Education at Oxford University (AIEOU) is an interdisciplinary hub designed to support a research-informed, ethical, human-centered approach to AIED that supports the diverse needs of the global educational landscape through collaboration and knowledge exchange. AIEOU has established an initial network of members including academics from across the University alongside academic peers, educators, learners, foundations, governments and industry partners from around the world who are all committed to safely and responsibly leveraging the potential of AIED. Together, they will explore the potential and pitfalls of AIED to discover how a collaborative approach can help pave the way forward across the four research pillars of design, regulation, implementation and impact.

The hub will address critical challenges associated with AIED. Challenges that can best be attended to by those who understand teaching and learning in collaboration with those who have a vested interest in achieving quality education for all. The interdisciplinary nature of the hub will facilitate a holistic approach to AIED. By combining insights from different disciplines, the hub will generate comprehensive solutions that consider the diverse needs of students, educators, and policymakers.

Over the next decade, the global edtech market is expected to reach US\$549 billion, and the AI in Education (AIED) market is forecast to reach US\$88.2 billion. Yet, despite the enormity of the market, the educational value of many digital tools remains contested. If, as Hawking predicted, AI will transform every aspect of our lives then an interdisciplinary approach is essential to ensure all stakeholders are represented. We must work collaboratively to ensure that we are able to make research-informed decisions and that AIED serves the needs of society and its young people well. We submit that it is important that such conversations are convened by educators in collaboration with end users, technologists, and other key stakeholders to best represent the needs of the learner.

Keywords: AI, education, interdisciplinary, leadership.

1 INTRODUCTION

“Anyone who wishes to cope with the future should travel back in imagination in a single lifetime – say to 1900 – and ask just how much of today’s technology would be, not merely incredible, but incomprehensible to the keenest scientific brains of that time.”

(Arthur C. Clarke, 1962).

In *Profiles of the Future*, Arthur C. Clarke (1962) shared that it is impossible to predict the future. Yet, in their daily work educators are tasked with the challenge of preparing our young people for it. In addition to this seemingly impossible task, teachers now also face the rapid evolution of generative AI technologies and edtech tools that are infiltrating their classrooms, pedagogy and practice. The future remains unpredictable yet appears to be entering classrooms faster than ever before. We don’t need to travel as far back as 1900 to appreciate this. Just turn back the clock three years and the technologies emerging in our classrooms today were incomprehensible to the majority of us.

In conversation with a representative from a national ministry of education, a call for help was issued. Their teachers were found to be overwhelmed by a tsunami of information about the perils and potential of AI that, for the most part, was not evidence-based or research informed. Implementation was haphazard, impact was unknown and regulation was in draft only. Speaking to other governments and

ministries of education, the feeling was shared. Looking to address these challenges and support educators globally, a vision emerged for an interdisciplinary research hub that could convene stakeholders, generate evidence and translate research into practice with the support of those who understand teaching and learning best, educators.

After successfully responding to a call for funding, the AI in Education at Oxford University (AIEOU) interdisciplinary research hub was established in December 2024. This paper explores the process undertaken to conceptualize the hub and establish it as a dynamic, virtual space convening hundreds of collaborators from across the world. The Hub aims to support the diverse needs of the global educational landscape through collaboration and knowledge exchange. In doing so, it aims not just to prepare students for their future but to also help them create the future they want by involving them in the creation of our shared research agenda when it comes to AIED.

2 METHODOLOGY

Inspired to establish the AIEOU Hub, the researchers sought to conceptualize their vision through theoretical frameworks that support the proposed research methodology. Grounded in the tenets of collaboration, knowledge exchange and seeking to maximize engagement with key stakeholders, the following approaches were adopted.

2.1 Systems theory

Systems theory matches the interdisciplinary approach taken by AIEOU as it serves to examine a phenomenon holistically, shifting our attention from the individual parts of the education system to view the impact of AIED as a whole. Through the observation and participation of educators, schools, students and policymakers, Systems theory supports the examination of impact on both the individual parts and the whole education system through the lens of shared purpose. The theory emphasizes the importance of viewing systems not as a composite of parts but as an integrated whole, where the interactions between parts gain significance (Mele et al., 2010). Systems theory supports a global vision to better comprehend the impact of AIED.

Viewing AIED through the lens of Systems theory affords us a multilevel analysis highlighting the interplay between technology and society. Thus, offering the opportunity to engage in 'what if?' scenarios where researchers can examine the unintended consequences and mitigate systemic inequities such as bias in algorithms and inequity of access.

The design of the AIEOU interdisciplinary research hub was informed by Systems theory to embrace the interconnected systems that are a feature of the global education landscape. It serves to promote the cross-disciplinary collaboration we seek and engages stakeholders to examine the challenge in a dynamic and robust way. The researchers examining the impacts of AIED must be as diverse as the society being examined to ensure a comprehensive and multidimensional approach.

2.2 Participatory research

Participatory research (PR) facilitates a sequential process of reflection and action that is undertaken by local people rather than on them (Cornwall & Jewkes, 1995). Such an approach places value on the knowledge and perspective that those working in classrooms and educational institutions bring to the research on AIED.

Cornwall & Jewkes (1995) argue that the key element of PR is not the methods but the attitudes of the researchers which determine how and for whom the research is undertaken. Key to this is the location of power in the research dynamic. A question that presents personal, political and professional considerations for those involved. Informed by Freire's (1972) approach to the power relations which permeate research and those it involves, PR aims to confront disparity of access whilst affirming that people's knowledge and lived experience is valuable. Our conception of PR affords AIEOU collaborators agency rather than viewing them as objects to be studied. Challenged by the question as to the role of the researcher in such a study, we opt to position ourselves as facilitators and convenors as we work to hold space for those wishing to engage in mutual learning and analysis that will shape and inform their actions as a result.

AIEOU includes academics from across the University of Oxford and around the world including disciplines such as Education, Psychology, Law, Computer Science, Engineering, Business, Finance, Linguistics, Creative Arts and Humanities. These academics work in collaboration with educators,

students, technologists, industry partners, foundations, charities, policy makers and others to promote a research-informed, ethical, human-centered approach to AIED through collaboration and knowledge exchange. Building on its interdisciplinary nature, the AIEOU Hub employs a PR approach to involve collaborators as co-researchers, reflecting System Theory's emphasis on interconnectedness and local, contextual factors.

The inclusion of key stakeholders in PR aligns with the aim of the Hub to establish a dynamic community of practice (Wenger, 1998) that will challenge and positively shape the future of AIED. PR is an effective approach given its emphasis on the co-creation of knowledge, shared ownership of research outcomes, and empowering participants to address issues that are meaningful to them. In the context of studying AIED, PR can help ensure that the design, regulation, implementation, and impact reflect the needs, values, and lived experiences of educators, students, and other stakeholders.

Drawing on the reflexive, flexible and iterative characteristics of PR (Cornwall & Jewkes, 1995), the AIEOU Hub engages local experts and stakeholders as active contributors and collaborators. Data collection involves all collaborators in gathering data, sharing knowledge, contributing to discussion groups and mapping impact. This process of reflection and action will take place over the life span of the Hub and the data will be used by the collaborators to design specific research projects, policy briefs, concept notes and guidance where appropriate.

2.3 Community of practice

In conceptualizing the AIEOU Hub, we embraced Wenger's (1998) definition of a community of practice (CoP) as "a group that coheres through mutual engagement on an indigenous (or appropriated) enterprise and creates a common repertoire" (p.125). The notion of community speaks to our shared vision for a globally inclusive, interdisciplinary research hub. The reference to practice denotes our focus on generating knowledge for action and the active translation of research into best practice, pedagogy, and policy.

The establishment of a CoP resonates with the intended research-informed, ethical, human-centered approach to AIED. Education is inherently human and though we may explore the potential of AI as we look to the future, there was an overwhelming need to convene and exchange knowledge in a manner that facilitated a sense of belonging, collegiality and humanity amongst the collaborators.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Early adoption

Upon launching the Hub on 1 December 2024, it quickly amassed considerable interest, growing in size by 1085% in the first ten days. Thus, evidencing the global consensus on the research and validating the critical importance of the issue to interested stakeholders. Figure 1 below is drawn from Google Analytics and shows the location of early adopters engaged with AIEOU.

Figure 1. Map of participants

In less than a month we have registered interest from more than 500 stakeholders who wish to collaborate with AIEOU to help evidence the impact and shape the future of AIED. Organically, we have achieved strong gender parity amongst the collaborators as shown in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Participants by gender

3.2 Research streams

Given the enormity of the challenge to address, four research streams were assigned to help navigate our study of AIED. These streams were chosen with a dual purpose in mind. Firstly, to support the interdisciplinarity of AIEOU research streams they were designated to speak to certain fields of study. For example, examining AIED through the lens of regulation was well suited to our academic colleagues in the Faculty of Law. Similarly, the Design research stream was aligned to the AIED research interests of our academic colleagues in Computer Science and Engineering. Secondly, the research streams were designed to support educators globally by affording them insight and agency pertinent to the design of AI tools, their regulation, their implementation in educational institutions and finally, their impact on student learning outcomes and teachers' work. As an additional consequence of this structure, AIEOU collaborators naturally aligned to the streams that were most relevant to their role. For example, our industry partners predominantly engage with the design research stream whilst our policy makers conversed between the regulation and implementation streams.

Figure 3. AIEOU Research Streams

3.3 Work in progress

3.3.1 Knowledge exchange

Through the establishment of AIEOU, we are forging collaborations and knowledge exchange across the University of Oxford and with external stakeholders. Our goal is to maximise the impact of our work

relating to the four research pillars of design, regulation, implementation and impact across the global educational landscape. To this effect, the first month has seen us generate more than 6000 visitors to the website and the publication of blog posts from collaborators in India, England and Tunisia. The establishment of digital spaces for collaborators to connect and the launch of the website is now complete in readiness for an increased flow of content and collaboration. We have also welcomed visitors from educational institutions in Singapore and across the UK to discuss shared research interests pertaining to AIED.

In a survey of AIEOU collaborators two weeks after the Hub's launch, 80% of respondents reported engaging in knowledge exchange with other members of the Hub. When asked, "what impact has AIEOU had on your working life this week?", one participant shared, "I have loads of new LinkedIn connections and I am submitting for a new book chapter with one as a result". Another responded, "For me, learning about excellent work by other members is a great experience."

3.3.2 Theory of change workshop

Following PR methodology, the AIEOU Hub commenced by identifying the issue and defining the problem. The high level of interest and uptake has proven the need to engage in this work. To further co-define the problem, a Theory of Change workshop is planned where participants will come together to ascertain the key objectives and planned outcomes. The Theory of Change (ToC) approach (Weiss, 1995) is suitably aligned to PR and will serve to afford the participants agency and voice as we co-create a shared research agenda.

Connell & Kubisch (1998) proposed that ToC can be used both for programme development and evaluation. As AIEOU collaborators engage in a participatory process of reflection and action, ToC workshops will be held at regular intervals.

3.3.3 Youth advisory board

Given that co-designing our shared research agenda is the next step for AIEOU, a process yet to commence is the development of a Youth Advisory Board comprised of high school students. The amplification of student voice in the examination of the potential roadmap for AIED is paramount to our vision as we put teachers and learners at the heart of the journey.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The aims and objectives of AIEOU are driven by an approach that examines AIED by the people most involved and for the people that will be impacted by it the most. That is, the teachers and educators in educational institutions around the world. Education has always been, and remains, a dynamic and evolving field of endeavour that works to make probable the seemingly impossible. If, as Hawking predicted, AI will transform every aspect of our lives then a collaborative, interdisciplinary approach is imperative to ensure all stakeholders are represented. Teachers and students must be afforded the loudest voice in shaping the future of education in an AI influenced context. It is only by coming together with shared goals and purpose that we can positively shape the design, regulation, implementation and impact of AIED in alignment with pedagogical best practice. As one collaborator stated, "we need this hub to bring together the best minds to help distil and disseminate the research in a way that we, the educators, can easily access and trust."

In conclusion, to revert once more to the words of Arthur C. Clarke (1962), the future is not to be forecast but created. AIEOU has been established with the goal of helping to positively shape the future of AIED in a manner that celebrates all that it is to be human whilst embracing the potential of AI ethically, responsibly and equitably. A goal that can only be achieved through collaboration and collective effort.

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